

ISic4353

I.Sicily inscription 4353

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2016.05.12

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance

area of the rione Forca

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo di Archeologia
dell'Universita di Catania, inventory 05/102

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:****Bibliography**

Biondi, G., Buscemi Felici, G. 2014. Iscrizioni. In Biondi, G., Buscemi Felici, G., Tortorici, E.(eds.), *Il museo archeologico dell'Università di Catania. Collezione Libertini*. Acireale. pp. 170-173. At 171 no.242 fig.42

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic4353. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4390368>